

A PROPOSAL OF PREDICTION METHOD OF COMPRESSIVE RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF IMPACT-DAMAGED CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, a new prediction method for compressive-after-impact (CAI) strength of CFRP laminates is proposed. Vibration pattern imaging technique and finite element method are applied to characterize the dynamic response of the impact-damaged specimen. A new finite element model is proposed for the impact-damaged region in which the stiffness reduction is expressed as equivalent thickness degradation. The model is applied to buckling analysis of the damaged specimen. The agreement between the numerical and experimental results of CAI strength is good, and the results indicate that the procedure could be applicable as a non-destructive prediction method.

INTRODUCTION

In the service condition, non-destructive evaluation plays a critical role in durability and reliability assessment of advanced composite structures [1]. Recently, many experimental investigations have been carried out on the characteristics of CAI strength [2-4]. Numerical analysis has also been applied when the size and the shape of the damaged region were given. However, prediction only by numerical results does not explain experimental results accurately, and the results are limited to a qualitative understanding of the phenomenon[5]. Therefore, the experimental approach is important for estimating the degradation of the CAI strength.

In the present study, the stiffness reduction of impact-damaged region was detected as a shift of the eigen frequency. The stiffness reduction was evaluated as an equivalent thickness degradation in combination a numerical analysis model. In order to predict the compressive strength of impact-damaged specimen, a numerical buckling analysis, which includes a region of thickness reduction, was carried out and investigated.

PROCEDURE FOR PREDICTING CAI STRENGTH

Figure 1 explains a flowchart of procedure for the present study. In general, delamination in laminates occurs due to impact loading. Delamination leads to decrease in both CAI strength and stiffness. Decrease in CAI strength also implies a decrease in buckling strength, and decrease in stiffness leads to a drop in eigen frequency as well. Therefore, a rectangular specimen was damaged using

a drop-weight impact tester. The damaged area of the specimen was detected using an ultrasonic C-scan instrument. The eigen frequency and the vibration mode of the specimen were measured by using the Laser Doppler vibrometer. Dynamic eigen analysis was carried out by the finite element method by reducing the thickness of the damaged region. After comparing the experimental and numerical results of the eigen frequency, the equivalent thickness degradation was predicted. The numerical buckling load was calculated with the equivalent thickness model of the damaged region. Finally, validity of the present approach was discussed by comparing the experimental results with the numerical results of the compressive strength.

Fig.1 Flowchart of non-destructive method for estimation of CAI strength

COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT TESTS

MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

Three types of carbon fiber were used in this study. The properties of the fibers and the matrix, i.e. three different pre-preg sheets are listed in Table 1. They are PAN-based HTA-12K fiber reinforced 120°C(250°F)-cured extensive use epoxy #113, PAN based IM600-12K fiber and 180°C(350°F)-cured toughened epoxy #134, and PAN-based T800₁₁ fiber and 180°C(350°F)-cured interlayer-toughened epoxy #3900-2 including fine particles of amorphous polyamide in the interlayer. The size of a specimen was 150mm long, 50mm wide and 2.3mm thick. The specimens were quasi

Table 1 Fibers and the matrix properties of three different composites

	Epoxy composites	Toughened-epoxy composites	Interlayer-toughened-epoxy composites
Carbon fiber	Besfight HTA-12K	Besfight IM600-12K	Toray T800-H
Tensile strength (MPa)	4032	5760	5590
Tensile modulus (GPa)	237	286	295
Matrix	Toho #113	Toho #134	Toray #3900-2

used as reference. The size of SACMA's specimen was 150mm long, 100mm wide and 4.6mm thick. Quasi isotropic (+45/0/-45/90)4S laminates were used. The size of the new type of specimen was 200mm long, 40mm wide and 2.3mm thick. The specimen were (+45/0/-45/90)2S laminates, and an additional device was used to prevent buckling of the specimen while loading.

IMPACT DAMAGE

Impact load was applied by using an instrumented drop-weight impact tester. A drop weight with a steel semi-spherical tip was used as an impactor. The total weight of the impactor was 1kg and the radius of the tip was 8mm. The specimen was mounted between the supporting steel plates with cut-out hole of 15mm in radius as shown in Fig. 2. The point of impact damage was located at the center of front surface of the specimen. Maximum impact energy of 2.5J/mm was applied on the (+45/0/-45/90)2S laminates. The damage area was detected after impact with the specimen in water, using ultrasonic C-scan instrument with 10MHz sensor.

COMPRESSION TEST

Figure 3 shows a photograph of the compression test fixture, which was modified and developed from our past experience in compression testing of glass fiber composites. The fixture does not use any additional device for preventing buckling of the specimen. The initial dead load due to the upper fixture was 0.04kgf/mm² (0.4MPa) for the specimen, and this effect is negligible.

Fig. 2 Spherical tip of drop weight impact tester and clamping device for specimen

Fig. 3 Modified compressive test fixture and a failed specimen

VIBRATION TEST

The Laser Doppler vibrometer was used as a non-contacting transducer for measuring vibration in the specimen. VPI 9000 system of Ometron Ltd., U.K., was used for the experiment. A single-beam back-scatter arrangement was adopted, and light reflected back from the specimen surface shifts in frequency by an amount equal to $2v/\lambda$, where v is the velocity of specimen surface and λ is

Fig. 4 Cantilever vibration specimen with impact damage and the supporting condition

the wave length of the laser radiation. Data acquisition is controlled by computer and raster scans are produced in the VPI 9000 system. Full field images of vibration pattern permits correlation between experimental and computational methods on the basis of similar degrees of freedom. Fig. 4 shows the cantilever specimen and the supporting conditions. The fixed end of the specimen was mounted on the vibrator and out-of-plane vibration was applied on the end of the specimen. The eigen frequency was determined by measuring the frequency of maximum amplitude of specimen response.

NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

Dynamic eigen value analysis and buckling analysis were carried out by using finite element analysis code, MARC k3 version. An isoparametric 8-node thick shell element was employed for finite element modeling of the specimen. The elastic properties of the shell element was calculated from the lamina properties, based on the lamination theory. The projected profile of the impact damage region was defined as a circle. In the present study, the stiffness degradation of the damaged region induced by the impact load, was adopted as the equivalent thickness degradation. That is, the damage region was modeled as a decrease in the thickness, as shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5 Equivalent thickness concept applied to a cross section in an impact damaged region

VIBRATION ANALYSIS

Parametric study was carried out by reducing the thickness, and the eigen frequency of the thickness were calculated. The most suitable equivalent thickness for finite element modeling of the damaged region was obtained by the least squares method using the experimental and calculated eigen frequency. An example of the mesh division is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Mesh with impact-damaged region

BUCKLING ANALYSIS

The buckling load was calculated by linear buckling analysis. A finite element model similar to the vibration analysis was adopted. The effect of local buckling and crack extension at the tips of delamination were not considered in the present analysis. 50mm from both ends of the specimen were fixed to prevent rotation, and a compression load was applied from one end.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IMPACT ENERGY AND DAMAGE AREA

The relation between the impact energy and the radius of the damaged area is shown in Fig.7. It is evident that the radius is saturated at a certain value. The radius depends on the material and also depends on the size of cut-out hole of the supporting steel plates. Figure 8 shows an example of Ultrasonic C-scan images of impact-damaged epoxy composites.

Fig. 7 Relation between the impact energy and the radius of the damaged area

Fig. 8 Ultrasonic C-scan images of impact-damaged epoxy composites

IMPACT ENERGY AND EIGEN FREQUENCY

Experimental examples of the third torsional mode of the toughened epoxy specimen and the fourth bending mode of the interlayer-toughened specimen are shown in Fig 9 and Fig.10, respectively. It was difficult to distinguish the vibration pattern visually in the low frequency domain. However, it is observed that the spacing and the shape of node lines are affected by the existence of impact damage in the high frequency domain. A common observation for the three kinds of composites was a remarkable decrease in eigen frequency at high order vibration modes, i.e. sixth and seventh mode, according to the increase in impact energy, as shown in Fig.11. On the other hand, there was no decrease in eigen frequency at low order vibration modes.

No-damaged specimen

No-damaged specimen

Damaged specimen by 2.5J/mm impact energy

Damaged specimen by 10J/mm impact energy

Fig. 9 The third vibration mode for coupled torsion of toughened composites

Fig. 10 The fourth vibration mode of inter-layer toughened epoxy composites

Fig. 11 Change of eigen frequency according to an increase in impact energy

BUCKLING ANALYSIS

Fig.12 shows the relation between numerical buckling strength and experimental compressive strength as a typical example for epoxy composites. The figure indicates that in the case of specimens with no impact damage, experimental values are considerably lower than numerical values. The reason is local failure which occurred at the supporting edges of the specimen as shown in Fig.13. For impact-damaged specimens, experimental and numerical results showed good agreement as shown in Fig.12. Fig.14 represents the relation between impact energy and CAI strength. The curved line and plots of filled dots indicate calculated and experimental values, respectively. It shows that the CAI strength can be estimated well by the impact energy for damaged specimens. Finally, Fig.15 shows the relation between the impact energy and the experimental compressive strength of epoxy-composite specimens. The values were obtained from three compressive methods, i.e. the SACMA and small rectangular methods with and without any additional device to prevent buckling of the specimen. The result indicates approximately same level at low, which means that the result does not depend entirely on the specimen size.

Fig. 12 Relation between numerical and experimental compressive strength

Fig. 13 Side-view of failure modes for toughened-epoxy composites in compression

(a) Epoxy composites

(b) Toughened-epoxy composites

(c) Interlayer-toughened-epoxy composites

Fig. 14 Relation between impact energy and CAI strength

Fig. 15 Relation between impact energy and experimental CAI strength for the three methods

CONCLUSIONS

By combining experimental and numerical methods, i.e. the so-called Hybrid experimental and computational mechanics approach, the CAI strength of the impact laminates could be estimated by non-destructive means. The results are summarized as follow.

1. A new finite model was proposed for the impact-damage region. The projected profile of the region was defined as a circle, and stiffness reduction was expressed as equivalent thickness degradation.
2. A new non-destructive testing method was proposed to estimate CAI strength by performing a vibration test.

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